

TEACHING VOCABULARY FOR YOUNG LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the sphere of methodology and teaching. The main purpose of the article is analyzing the main games and activities of vocabulary that can be implemented for teaching young learners. The article is associated with different professor's analysis and experience, such as psychologist M. Vohidov and methodologist J. Jalolov. All the activities have been analysed during the lessons.

Keywords: language proficiency, the content of teaching vocabulary, sub skills, sufficient vocabulary.

Introduction. Currently the English language is a universal language and significant steps are being taken by the education system of Uzbekistan to develop the system of teaching English as a foreign language. The Presidential Decree №1875- "On measures of improvement of learning foreign languages" contributes a noteworthy progress of teaching English as a foreign language in the educational institutions of Uzbekistan. One of the aim of the Presidential Decree is to teach foreign language from the first form. Therefore EFL teachers should know how to teach language proficiency (reading, listening, speaking and writing), and its sub skills (vocabulary, grammar and phonetics). In this article readers can be acquainted with the importance of teaching vocabulary, choosing appropriate topics for teaching vocabulary for A1 pupils and making the teaching process interesting and effective through games.

Teaching vocabulary is a significant objective in the curriculum. According to psychologists (M. Vohidov. "Children's psychology" 1982), human beings learn life experiences by words, because thoughts are made by words. Without a sufficient vocabulary, learners cannot communicate and express ideas effectively. Teaching new words for pupils at primary schools is very fruitful and is considered the basic foundation of teaching English, as for communicating, constructing sentences and understanding oral and written speech, young learners should know English words.

Some EFL teachers at primary education come across some difficulties with choosing an appropriate topic for teaching vocabulary. There is a standard that is all requirements and content of teaching vocabulary are given. The content of teaching vocabulary is dedicated to A1 learners. A1 learners are the pupils of primary school. According to the standard of teaching foreign languages in Uzbekistan A1 learners should learn some words of simple topics such as family, fruits, vegetables, animals and etc. They should be aware of some concepts about word-formation and borrowings.

Jalolov states that children (ages 5-12) are very much orientated in their minds around the “here and now” and directly visible or perceivable environment. If EFL teacher only explains the words and he or she does not give examples, this teaching process does not show any results. Therefore, English teachers should use different visual materials and interesting activities that capture young learner’s attention. Moreover, young learners remember the new words when they see and touch. That is why, it is pointed that different games and activities help the learners to understand the meaning of the new word and using it in communication.

Recently, I have observed the English lessons at primary school. The lesson was full of enjoyable games and demonstrating materials for introducing new topic. I witnessed different games that give essential benefits.

The first game is called “**The stork came**”. Actually, this game is our national game, however, the teacher made it suitable for teaching vocabulary. This game is very profitable for the learners of the first form. If the pupils are learning the names of weekdays or numbers, this game is appropriate. For doing this activity, pupils work in groups (maximum 6 participants). One of the participants should tell the number or the name of weekday. Then they clap each other’s hand by telling the numbers or days in order. When mentioned number or day comes with clapping, the participant loses the game. Through this game learners remember the numbers and days easily.

The next game is named “**Family tree**”. After the first presentation stage, this activity is fruitful for strengthening the topic. For this game pupils are divided into 2 groups. Women family tree is for the first group, and men family tree is for another group. The members of each group write the names of family members according to their gender on the family tree that is on the blackboard. This game does not only make young learners remember the names of family members, but also it lets students work in the group with responsibility.

The third game that I observed is called “**Find it**”. I mentioned above that most young learners are visual and tactile learners. This game is very helpful for working with realia. The pupils that I observed learned how to call wild and domestic animals in English in the first stage. Then in the second stage, they played this activity. This game is dedicated for working individually. For this game, one pupil comes on the blackboard and closes eyes with strap. Then teacher puts different animal toys on the desk. The pupil chooses one of them and defines the animal and tells the name of it by touching it. This game is also considered very useful activity for teaching vocabulary for young learners.

Taking all the things into consideration, we can conclude that for teaching foreign language for the elementary level learners, we should pay our most attention to teach its vocabulary. As vocabulary is considered an important part of the foreign languages for communicating and comprehending. In the past choosing appropriate topics for teaching vocabulary for young learners was difficult. However, nowadays we have our national standard for teaching foreign languages. Therefore teachers easily can choose suitable topics for young pupils. Moreover, there are different games and activities for making the process of teaching vocabulary, interesting, effective and enjoyable. Nowadays EFL teachers are using these games and, they are witnessing positive results.

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